

INCREASING THE POSITIVE MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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English language

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Annotation: This article devoted to open the important points about increasing the positive motivation of students in teaching foreign languages. Moreover, types of motivation and its significant function in the education process were highlighted.

Key words: *new horizons, 'productive failure', unfamiliar concepts, "hard-care" reputations, exercise program, individual activity, language community, instrumental motivation.*

Learning Foreign languages has become a necessity and trend these days. On the educational point of view, including foreign language as a side subject provides a new insight for children belonging to the age group between 4 to 5 years old. It improves their listening, speaking, writing and reading skills efficiently, ultimately resulting in an overall development of a child's mental sharpness. As per statistical survey conducted by Ministry of Education, it has been found that creative and logical skills of children having knowledge of foreign language are much stronger as compared to other children. Learning a new language provides two benefits: first, one can approach to new horizons and second, one becomes able to build up its own identity resulting into self-confidence build-up. It not only builds up self-confidence but also helps an individual to improve its overall personality. Zeal and passion for learning new languages is growing gradually among people when they are realizing its vitality in grooming one's personality[1]. Hence, everybody's is making them their cup of tea. Learning a foreign language is the best way to

understand our own language (mother tongue) and its culture and other aspects in a more detailed way through comparison between them.

Learning something and making mistakes is part of the process. More than that; mistakes are a good thing! This is a key concept of education: 'productive failure', making mistakes and learning from them, is one of the most effective ways to learn something. In recent years, Manu Kapur, currently a professor of Psychological Studies at The Education University of Hong Kong, conceptualized the notion of productive failure, the learning process based on learning from mistakes. According to Kapur, research illustrates that it is very effective to let students fail around with unfamiliar concepts, even when they are still lacking the knowledge and skills to solve all problems correctly. The students who sit in the back of the classroom and refuse to try a new assignment usually are afraid they cannot do the work and they cannot risk their "hard-care" reputations by making mistakes in public. The students who claim that they are bored that the lesson is too easy are quite often afraid that they cannot do the work either. Perhaps, a few of those students are self-destructive. Students try when they believe they can succeed. On the other hand, if they believe they will fail, they will refuse to try. You can help your students develop self-confidence and faith in their ability to learn by allowing them to make mistakes. Von Oech explains: "Most people consider success and failure as opposites but they are actually both products of the same process. The same energy which generates good creative ideas also produces errors." He goes on to discuss ways to use errors as stepping stones to success and how to use negative feedback in a positive manner.

Most students learn English because they believe it will benefit them in one way. They want to earn more money to fulfil certain education requirements, to travel abroad or to meet more people with the aid of English. Without strong motivation, students will fail in their attempt and their hopes of learning. Motivation is a central topic in the field of education. At the same time, this is one of the most

critical topics. Motivation is vital in language learning. One of the most difficult aspects of teaching is how to motivate a language student. The secret is identifying the students' motivation then making the lesson relevant and enjoyable. Motivation is a complex human construct that has long posed difficulties for those who attempt to understand and explain it[2]. The issue of increasing motivation, retention and development of students' interest to the subject "foreign language" attracted much attention, both in psychology and in the methods of teaching the subject. Response can be attributed to:

1) the creation of a specially designed exercise program, by performing that students would feel the result of its operations;

2) When learning a new language is possible to apply in such exercises like crossword puzzles, drawing on history image. For example, the game "Find the word". We give grid cells, each cell is written letter of the alphabet. Among the set of letters hidden words on the "program" topic. Students must find the words, that have been found in the list, and translate. Instructions :

3) Words can be written forward, backward, vertically; horizontally, or diagonally all words related to the theme of "program".

4) You should look for the following words, mark them on the grid and write transfer to the side so that you understand their meaning.

5) Crossword can be used not only as individual activity of the child, but as a collective also. Class is divided into two groups (A and B). Make up crossword with words on the topic, then all the words of a crossword puzzle equally divided, is 2 blank forms, one of them is filled with a part of the word, the other — the second, so that they complement each other. One form is given by the group A, the other — Group B. In order to fill a crossword puzzle requires the participation of two groups: Group A Group B explains the meaning of those words that are in its form, and then change the group[3]. Motivation is a basic and essential part of learning. Gardner, believes that with the intention of being motivated, the learner

necessitates, requires, and needs to have something to anticipate, foresee, expect and long for, a reason, principle, or rationale having to do with aim or target. Concerning second/foreign language acquisition, this intention would be learning a foreign language. In fact, there must be something that the learner desires to achieve or do, being the target language the vehicle to attain it. According to Cook the performance and presentation of a number of learners in the context of second or foreign language learning is improved and superior than others. The reason is that they are better motivated.

Ellis sees the incident of learning by means of motivation and believes that the learning process simply occurs when a person is motivated. Relating to this matter, Ellis says that “language teachers readily acknowledge the importance of learners’ motivation, not infrequently explaining their own sense of failure with reference to their students’ lack of motivation”[4]. Cook states that acquisition of language is not the same among learners. He also believes that there are three main factors which influence the Second Language Acquisition. These three factors are: age, personality and motivation. Motivation is the most significant factor among the mentioned three factors that affect second language acquisition. Ellis suggests that motivation is “the effort which learners put into learning an L2 as a result of their need or desire to learn it”. Also, Lightbrown and Spada identify motivation in SLA as an intricate incident which can be identified along with two factors: “learners’ communicative needs and their attitudes towards the second language community”. They believe that when learners think that they need to speak the second language with the aim of being in touch with others or accomplishing and achieving specialized desires and goals, they will be motivated to obtain expertise and skill in it. Gardner and Lambert name the mentioned situation as integrative motivation and instrumental motivation. Research has proved that whether second language learning is successful or not directly and strongly concerns with these types of motivation[5].

In a summary, it should be noted that motivated students are every teacher's dream — they are willing to work hard, add their own goals to those of the classroom, focus their attention on the tasks at hand, persevere through challenges, don't need continuous encouragement, and may even stimulate others in the classroom, promoting collaborative learning. However, we all know that the motivation behind our students' learning varies widely, ebbs and flows over the course of the year (or even during a single classroom activity), and stems from various sources, internal to the learner, external, or both. As teachers we can generally see who is motivated and who is not, and often we may wonder how or even if we can harness the motivation of some and spread it out to others. Tapping into motivation is crucial for language teachers because we know that motivation is one of the key factors driving language learning success. In fact, teachers often see it as their job to motivate students by creating classroom tasks that are interesting and engaging and by using authentic materials to stimulate further interest in the language and the people who speak it. Over the last twenty years, research on motivation for foreign language learning has evolved considerably from focusing on describing what composes student motivation to a detailed list of suggestions that help teachers initiate, sustain, and further promote student motivation.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that education is important because students must know and learn things that have occurred from the past to date. This helps to create new ideas for students to put into practice in the future. After graduating high school, students must think and know the next step to take. Most students want to continue to have further education in their professions and want to be above their dreams, to show others that it is possible. Others give up their education, maybe because it is not affordable to get in and do not want to risk falling into debt; it could also be because they were not accepted in any school. Getting to a university is a struggle for most students because they need

transportation, living, and work as they will now be independent and will have to experience adulthood life.

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